

RADIOBLOCKS

Project ID: 101093934

Beamforming and Coherent Dedispersion Modules

Deliverable:	D4.5
Lead beneficiary:	JIV-ERIC
Submission date:	February 20, 2026
Dissemination level:	Public

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Abstract

In deliverable D4.4 we demonstrated that a basic correlator based on TensorCore architecture can deliver big improvements in both performance and efficiency. While a basic correlator covers a significant part of the science cases for the instruments used in the radio astronomy community, many other science cases require more advanced processing capabilities. Therefore we developed a few advanced correlator features: multiple phase center correlation, beamforming and coherent de-dispersion. These features were selected based on important science cases for the EVN and LOFAR, such as wide-field VLBI, pulsar and FRB observations.

This deliverable describes the implementation of these advanced features. They have been implemented as re-usable GPU radio blocks that can be combined with other radio blocks and can easily be integrated in the applications described in deliverable D4.4 to extend their functionality. We briefly describe the algorithms behind these radio blocks and the way they have been implemented and provide some details on how these radio blocks can be integrated in applications. We also evaluate their performance and energy efficiency showing that we can retain the significant gains described in deliverable D4.4 for these metrics. The radio blocks discussed in this deliverable are open source and archived on Zenodo.

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List of acronyms

API	Application Programming Interface
ASIC	Application Specific Integrated Circuit
ASTRON	Netherlands Institute for Radio Astronomy
COBALT	CORrelator and Beamformer Application for the LOFAR Telescope
CPU	Central Processing Unit
EVN	European VLBI Network
FFT	Fast Fourier Transform
FPGA	Field-Programmable Gate Array
FRB	Fast Radio Burst
GEMM	General Matrix Multiply
GPU	Graphics Processing Unit
JIVE, JIV-ERIC	Joint Institute for VLBI ERIC

LOFAR	Low Frequency Array
mas	milliarcsecond
MPC	Multiple Phase Center
SFXC	Super FX Correlator
TB	terabyte
TCC	Tensor-Core Correlator
VLBI	Very Long Baseline Interferometry

1 Introduction

This deliverable implements a few GPU radio blocks that implement more advanced correlator features. One of the major benefits of a correlator based on CPU technology is that it offers immense flexibility in implementing support for specific scientific needs compared to a correlator based on ASICs or FPGAs. Over the past 15 years, this flexibility has been exploited at the EVN correlator at JIVE to support many different science cases. More recently, we have seen that GPUs are much more energy efficient than CPUs and provide significantly more performance. But while GPU technology is also very flexible, there are additional constraints and programming challenges. In order to get a feeling whether GPUs are flexible enough to support a wide variety of science cases, we have chosen a few advanced correlator features and implemented GPU-based radio blocks for those features.

2 Radio Blocks

2.1 Multiple Phase Center correlation

2.1.1 Introduction

The first advanced feature that we implemented is support for correlating multiple phase centers. This is a technique developed by Deller et.al. [1] to support wide-field VLBI. Wide-field VLBI can be challenging because of the high resolution that VLBI provides. In principle the field of view of an interferometer is the same as the field of view of the individual telescopes that form the interferometer; for a heterogeneous arrays like the EVN this field of view is typically restricted by the largest dish that participates in the observation. However, for VLBI there are practical limitations that further limit the field of view. One such limitation is that imaging that field of view is almost impossible due to the high resolution. For example, an image of the full field of view of an array of 25 m dishes at 5 mas resolution would be 1×10^{11} pixels or roughly 0.5 TB in size. Another practical limitation is that averaging in time and frequency by the correlator results in bandwidth and time smearing that limits the field of view. But without some degree of averaging the size of the correlator output quickly becomes unmanageable for the current generation of calibration and imaging software.

The fundamental idea behind multiple phase center correlation is to correlate at high frequency and time resolution, and phase shift to pre-determined

Figure 1: Multiple phase centers placed into the field of view of a VLBI array.

locations within the field of view of the telescopes (see figure 1) before averaging down in time and frequency. This results in multiple data sets of more manageable size, while limiting the effects of bandwidth and time smearing around the sources of interest.

2.1.2 Software Description

The source code for the multiple-phase-center correlator radio block can be found at [2]. It is expected that the source code for this radio block will evolve with the needs of applications. An archived version of the code that corresponds to this deliverable is available on Zenodo [3].

Two approaches to multiple phase center correlation have been implemented in this radio block as early benchmarking indicated limited scalability of the first implementation we tried. This first approach uses a feature of the Tensor Core Correlator [4] that allows specification of a user-defined function to store visibilities into GPU memory. Our implementation of this function applies, for each phase center, the appropriate phase shift to the visibility and writes it into a phase-center-specific position in the output visibility buffer. The downside of this approach is that implementing frequency averaging in the TCC GPU kernel is not possible when combined with the phase shifts required for the multiple phase center correlation. Therefore, frequency averaging has to be implemented separately. This could be done either on the GPU or the CPU. The former is probably preferable as this reduces the required bandwidth between

GPU and CPU memory on systems that do not have unified or hybrid memory. Since we can do frequency averaging after further time averaging, which is done once per output integration, we expect the computational cost of this additional step to be small.

The second approach uses the Tensor Core Correlator as-is and launches a second GPU kernel to do the phase shifting. This approach has the benefit that we can integrate efficient frequency averaging in this second GPU kernel as well. This reduces the amount of memory bandwidth that is needed to write out the visibilities for all the different phase centers. Therefore, it is no surprise that this second approach is more efficient for large number of phase centers.

Both implementations use the same API. This means that it is easy to switch between those two implementations. We anticipate that a production correlator would choose between the two implementations based on parameters such as the number of phase centers and the desired output frequency resolution. The most important parameters of the multiple phase center correlator radio block are:

inputFormat Sample input format; currently only `tcc:fp16` is supported.

nrReceivers Number of receivers (stations) in the array.

nrMPCChannels Number of output frequency channels; this determines the field of view of the individual phase centers.

nrChannels Number of internal frequency channels; this determines the internal frequency resolution and therefore the total field of view that can be used to place individual phase centers.

nrSamplesPerChannel Number of samples to integrate over; this determines the time resolution and therefore the total field of view that can be used to place individual phase centers.

nrSources The number of phase centers in the correlation.

baseFrequency Sky frequency for channel 0.

bandwidth Total bandwidth covered by the correlation.

nrPolarizations Number of polarizations per receiver; currently the only supported value is 2.

The frequency and bandwidth parameters are necessary to calculate the appropriate phase shifts based on the differential geometric delays between phase

centers and the original direction for which the high-resolution correlation products were calculated. This means that it is necessary to instantiate the radio block separately for each frequency band that is correlated. The application is expected to call the **launchAsync()** member function for each integration step. Compared to the same function in the tensor core correlator radio block this member function requires the application to pass the differential delays for all phase centers as an additional parameter. These differential delays should be passed as a 2-dimensional array with dimensions **[nrSources][nrReceivers]**. For the variant of the multiple phase center correlator that uses the user-defined function to store the Visibilities the differential delays are passed at the end of the visibility output buffer. To help the user allocate a buffer of the right size, a **visibilityBufferSize()** helper function is provided. The **launchAsync()** function takes care of copying the delays from host to device memory. The differential delays can be calculated using

$$\delta\tau'_i(t) = (\tau_i(t) - \tau'_i(t))(1 - \dot{\tau}_i(t)) \quad (1)$$

where $\tau_i(t)$ is the delay for the correlation center for receiver i at time t and $\tau'_i(t)$ is the delay for an additional phase center. This is essentially equation (4) in [5], adjusted for the delay sign convention used in our radio blocks.

An example of how to use the radio block is available in the source repository under `test/SimpleExample`. A benchmark application is also provided. This benchmark application can optionally use the Power Management Toolkit [6] to do power measurements and evaluate the efficiency of the implementation in joules per sample. Otherwise it just calculates the performance in input samples per second. To evaluate the performance of the code we have run the benchmark tools on an NVIDIA RTX PRO 4000 Blackwell GPU. The efficiency of the two implementations is plotted in figure 2 with the line that corresponds to linear scaling plotted as a reference. The performance (in input samples per second) is plotted in figure 3. Both plots are for an array of 16 stations, with an internal frequency resolution that corresponds to 2048 channels, averaged down to 64 channels. In the figures `MPCTCC.cu` corresponds to the implementation that uses the user-defined function to store visibilities, whereas `MPC.cu` corresponds to the implementation that uses the separate GPU kernel to implement the phase shifts. The plots clearly show that the `MPC.cu` implementation is faster for more than 40 phase centers but is already more efficient at 30 phase centers.

2.1.3 Applications

We anticipate that the multiple phase center correlator radio block will be used in a future GPU correlator for the EVN. Currently approximately 10% of all EVN

Figure 2: Efficiency of our implementations as a function of the number of phase centers (lower is better).

Figure 3: Performance of our implementations as a function of the number of phase centers (higher is better).

observations make use of the multiple phase center capability of the SFXC CPU correlator. This percentage is expected to grow in the near future with a growing interest in wide-field VLBI from the scientific community.

A relatively small number of these observations, those that use hundreds of phase centers, dominate the use of the current correlator. This is partly because the inefficient use of the current compute cluster that is used to run the correlator; the low amount of memory per core means only a subset of the available cores can actually be used during multiple phase center correlation. Therefore an efficient multiple phase center correlator GPU implementation that uses the available resources in a more optimal way is important for EVN operations.

2.2 Tensor-Core Beamformer

2.2.1 Introduction

Beamforming is a fundamental signal processing technique used in radio astronomy, medical imaging, and other sensing applications that employ sensor arrays. By coherently combining signals from multiple antennas or sensors with complex weights, beamforming forms directional beams that enhance signals from selected directions while suppressing interference and noise. The key challenge is that this operation is dominated by dense complex linear algebra and must be executed at very high data rates, often under real-time constraints.

In a digital beamformer, samples from an array of K sensors are multiplied by complex weights and summed over the sensor dimension to produce M output beams for N time samples. This operation can be written as the complex GEMM

$$\mathbf{Y} = \mathbf{W} \mathbf{X}, \quad (2)$$

where $\mathbf{X} \in \mathbb{C}^{K \times N}$ contains complex input samples (sensor \times time), $\mathbf{W} \in \mathbb{C}^{M \times K}$ contains the beamforming weights (beam \times sensor), and $\mathbf{Y} \in \mathbb{C}^{M \times N}$ contains the beamformed outputs (beam \times time). Each output sample is a dot product over K sensors, so the operation is dominated by multiply-accumulate work and maps naturally to matrix multiplication.

Modern GPUs include tensor cores that accelerate matrix multiplications at very high throughput. Although originally introduced for machine-learning workloads, tensor cores can be exploited for beamforming when the computation is expressed in a suitable matrix form and precision. We implement beamforming using tensor-core-accelerated complex GEMM kernels, and provide a reusable software stack centred around a flexible complex GEMM backend [7, 8].

2.2.2 Software description

To support tensor-core-accelerated beamforming, we developed the Common Complex GEMM Library (`ccglib`) [7, 8]. The library implements complex GEMM by decomposing it into real-valued matrix operations that can be executed efficiently on tensor cores. It supports mixed-precision configurations, flexible memory layouts, and both interleaved and planar (split) representations of complex numbers. The specific version of the library that corresponds to this deliverable has been archived on Zenodo [9].

The `ccglib` implementation includes built-in transpose and data-reordering functionality to place input matrices into the layout expected by the selected GEMM kernel. This step can also apply tiling to improve memory access patterns and increase arithmetic intensity, which is critical for sustaining tensor-core utilisation in the end-to-end beamforming pipeline.

On top of `ccglib`, we implemented a generic beamforming module that exposes a beamforming-oriented interface while delegating the performance-critical computation to the underlying complex GEMM kernels. In the LOFAR processing chain, `ccglib` is integrated in the coherent Stokes beamforming pipeline through `gpuproc` [10]. The integration target is the LOFAR real-time correlator and beamformer software stack (COBALT) [11], such that the optimised GEMM backend provided by `ccglib` can be used in the production system.

This separation between a reusable GEMM backend and application-specific pre-processing and post-processing keeps the implementation portable across instruments and data formats, while still allowing instrument-specific kernels (e.g., weight updates and format conversions) to be composed around a single high-throughput beamforming primitive.

The same design also supports very low input precisions. In a medical ultrasound beamforming setting, `ccglib` has been used with 1-bit input data to increase throughput and reduce memory bandwidth, while retaining sufficient numerical accuracy to produce a functional image.

The software targets NVIDIA GPUs with tensor cores starting with Volta-generation devices and is designed to be portable across newer architectures. In practice, we focus on Ada-generation GPUs because they are used in the COBALT3 system, which runs the software in production for LOFAR2 operations.

For LOFAR2, the current signal chain produces 8-bit complex samples; after filtering, these are converted to 16-bit complex floating-point values that are fed to the beamformer. The precision and layout flexibility in `ccglib` allow this path to be implemented efficiently while keeping the beamforming computation compatible with tensor-core kernels.

2.2.3 Applications

LOFAR time-domain radio astronomy In the LOFAR radio telescope, incoming complex voltage data from multiple stations are combined using direction-dependent beamforming weights to form coherent beams. By offloading the dominant matrix multiplication workload to tensor cores, the implementation delivers substantial performance improvements compared to conventional GPU kernels, enabling the production of more beams within the same computational budget [8].

Medical ultrasound imaging The same mathematical structure applies to medical ultrasound beamforming, but with different constraints on latency, power consumption, and data representation. The ability of `ccglib` to handle custom precisions and layouts enables efficient deployment in this setting, demonstrating the generality of the approach.

General applicability Any system in which beamforming can be expressed as complex matrix multiplication can benefit from this approach, including other radio telescopes, radar and sonar systems, and acoustic sensor arrays.

2.3 Coherent De-Dispersion

2.3.1 Introduction

Radio transients such as pulsars, and fast radio bursts (FRBs) are pulsed bursts of radio emission. An important property of these bursts is that they are dispersed by the interstellar-, and intergalactic media, i.e. receive a frequency dependent time delay. In Fig.4(a) we show a dispersed burst from FRB121102 as seen by the Arecibo radio telescope which clearly shows the frequency dependent delay.

The dispersive time delay τ_d between two frequencies ν_0 and ν_1 is given by

$$\tau_d \approx 4.15 \times 10^9 \times DM \times (\nu_1^{-2} - \nu_0^{-2}) \quad [\mu\text{s}], \quad (3)$$

where ν_0 , and ν_1 are in MHz, and DM is the dispersion measure, which is proportional to the number of free electrons along the line of sight to the source. Because the dispersive delay smears out the signal in time, it is necessary to compensate for this effect in order to maximize signal to noise ratio.

There are two common strategies to mitigate the effects of the dispersive delay: incoherent-, and coherent de-dispersion. In incoherent de-dispersion the data are correlated with a high enough number of frequency channels such that

Figure 4: (a) Dispersed pulse from FRB 121102 ($DM=561 \text{ pc} \cdot \text{cm}^{-3}$) as seen by the Arecibo dish (b) Pulse profile of FRB 121102 on the Arecibo - Effelsberg baseline obtained by coherently de-dispersing the data using the radio block described in the section.

the amount of smearing due to Eq. (3) is small. The frequency channels are then shifted in time according to the amount of dispersive delay that channel underwent. Although this scheme can generally be efficiently implemented, it breaks down when the size of the Fourier transform needed to obtain sufficient spectral resolution is a significant fraction of the duration of the burst.

These limitations are not present when using coherent de-dispersion. In this method a digital filter is applied to the data which removes the effect of dispersion from the signal, prior to correlation. The resulting de-dispersed time series can then be analyzed using a time-, and frequency resolution which is unrelated to what was used in the de-dispersion algorithm.

2.3.2 Software Description

We have created a GPU implementation of a coherent de-dispersion filter, which we distribute as a radio block, available at [12]. An archived version of the code that corresponds to this deliverable is available on Zenodo [13].

2.3.2.1 Implementation

The filter is implemented in an overlap-save structure, in which successive filter steps are half-overlapped. The algorithm can be divided into three steps:

1. The data are Fourier transformed using a fast Fourier transform (FFT). The

number of points in the FFT, N_{FFT} , is chosen such that the amount of dispersive smearing is less than 50% of the length of the FFT window.

For a sub-band of bandwidth BW , centered on frequency ν_c (both in MHz), we obtain using Eq.(3),

$$N_{FFT} > \text{sample rate} \times 16.6 \times 10^9 \times DM \times ((\nu_c - BW/2)^{-2} - \nu_c^{-2}), \quad (4)$$

where the sample rate is given in Msamples / second. Subsequent FFTs are half-overlapped.

2. Apply the filter using a GPU kernel. The transfer function of this filter is given by [14]

$$H(\nu_c + \nu) = \exp\left(\frac{-i2\pi\nu^2 DM}{2.41 \times 10^{-10}\nu_c^2(\nu_c + \nu)}\right), \quad (5)$$

where ν_c is the sub-band's centre frequency, and ν is the frequency offset relative to ν_c (both in MHz).

3. Apply an inverse FFT (IFFT) to the data, and copy the middle 50% of the results to an output array.

All FFTs are performed using NVIDIA's cuFFT library. A potential optimization would be to use an in-kernel FFT library such as cuFFTDX, so that all steps listed above could be combined into a single kernel. However, at present the cuFFTDX library is limited to FFTs of at most 32768 points, which is insufficient for the vast majority of cases.

For example, consider a 32 MHz band starting at 1600 MHz, observing a source with a modest $DM = 50 \text{ pc} \cdot \text{cm}^{-3}$. Filling these numbers in Eq. (4) yields a minimum FFT size of $N_{FFT} = 408857$, an order of magnitude larger than is supported by cuFFTDX.

2.3.2.2 Usage

The de-dispersion filter is implemented in the `libdedisp::Dedispersion` class defined in the include file `dedispersion.h`. The most important parameters for the constructor of this class are:

- **streams** Cuda streams to which the cuFFT plans will be bound.
- **channel** Frequency, bandwidth, sample rate, and sideband of the sub-band to be de-dispersed in Hz.

- **DM** The dispersion measure of the source
- **number_stations** Number of stations to be de-dispersed
- **fftsize** The size of the FFT to be used when applying the coherent de-dispersion filter. The class includes a helper to compute the minimum required fft size: `Dedispersion::fftsize_dedispersion`.
- **nfft_per_block** The number of FFTs to process in a single invocation of the filter.

The filter is applied using the `apply_dedispersion` method, which takes the following parameters

- **d_in** `nvRingBuffer` which contains the input data
- **d_out** `nvRingBuffer` to which the output data will be written
- **nfft** The number of ffts to process
- **streamnr** The cuda stream into which to run the de-dispersion algorithm

Note that the `nvRingBuffer` class, a simple ring buffer, is included in this radio block.

2.3.2.3 Results

In Fig.4(b) we show a pulse profile for FRB 121102 created using this radio block. The profile was created by dividing the pulse period into a number of time bins and then integrating the correlated data separately for each bin.

In Fig.5 we show the performance as a function of DM on an NVIDIA RTX PRO 4000 Blackwell GPU together with the FFT sizes used in the de-dispersion. Performance is roughly tracking with FFT size, with DM s that result in the same FFT size yielding identical performance. However, larger FFTs are not always slower in this case.

2.3.3 Applications

We intend to integrate the coherent de-dispersion radio block into a future EVN GPU correlator. The ability to perform coherent de-dispersion with our CPU based correlator [15] was instrumental to a number of important science results related to FRBs. However, due to the very large FFT- and filter lengths, applying coherent de-dispersion is very computationally expensive on a CPU. An efficient GPU implementation will significantly reduce the computational cost for these science cases.

Figure 5: Performance of de-dispersion radio block as a function of DM together with the number of points used in the FFTs. The run-times are normalized to the case where no de-dispersion is applied. The benchmark was performed by de-dispersing 50 s of dummy data using 16 stations.

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